

Leadership Influence Analysis and Emotional Intelligence on Employee Performance through Organizational Culture as a Mediation Variable

Desnizar, Tjiptogoro Dinarjo Soehari
Mercu Buana University, Jakarta Indonesia

Abstract:- Study This aim for analyze influencing factors performance employees, including: Leadership, intelligence emotional and cultural organization. Study this too want analyze influence leadership and intelligence emotional to culture organization as well as analyze How culture organization mediate influence leadership and intelligence emotional to performance employee. Population in study This totaling 90 employees remains in the Human Capital division at PT Tribhakti Inspektama. The sample used as many as 90 employees, the sampling used in study This is saturated sampling. Method research used is quantitative descriptive with SEM-PLS. Based on analysis on research This obtained results that: leadership influential positive and significant to culture organization; intelligence emotional influential positive and significant to culture organization; culture organization No influential to performance employees; leadership No influential significant to performance employee.; intelligence emotional influential positive and significant to performance employees; culture organization No mediate leadership to performance employees; culture organization No mediate influence intelligence emotional to performance employee.

Keywords:- Leadership, Intelligence Emotional, Culture Organization, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Industry mining is one sector important in development economy in Indonesia, provides material raw for production goods impact on growth economy sustainable national. Key success company is success company in manage employees, that done for reach vision mission company and can contribute in a manner significant to growth economy national. Many people assume that employees working in the sector mining own system clear work (systematic), planned, remuneration high, but on the other hand some industry neither does mining escape from related problems performance employee.

Interview results with GM Human Capital PT TBI who has Work for 4 years, results interview the is known there is problem with performance employee, where from results evaluation performance from 2019-2021 no There is One year that reached the target assessment existing performance determined by the company. Causing phenomenon performance employee No achieving this target is one of them is there is instability from results performance employees reflected in 2019 – 2021, where period 2019 – 2020 there enhancement results performance even though

No a lot, but in 2020-2021 experience decline although not many, from 2 strategic global aspects not even business fulfilled namely Growth and Stability so study about performance employee with objective For increase growth company and company stability That important .

Factor predictable factor often become reason No achievement of targets on performance employee among them leadership, intelligence emotional, cultural organization, Leadership, Commitment Organization, and Compensation. For now, factor which one has the most influence? change performance employees, researchers have done pre -survey of 22 people in the HC department of PT TBI. Study This furthermore will analyze influence leadership, and intelligence emotional to performance employee through culture organization as a mediating variable at PT Tribhakti Inspektama.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Employee Performance

According to Priansa (2018) performance is the embodiment of work results achieved by employees in carrying out tasks and jobs originating from the organization. According to Kasmir (2019) the factors that affect performance, both results and work behavior, are as follows: Ability and Expertise,; Knowledge,; Draft Work,; Personality,; Motivation Work,; Leadership,; Leadership style; Culture Organization; Satisfaction work; Environment work; Commitment; Discipline Work and Loyalty. (Bintoro and Daryanto, 2017) argued There is four influencing indicators performance employees, namely: (1) quality; (2) quantity; (3) responsibility answer; (4) initiative.

B. Maintaining the Integrity of the Specifications

(Siswanto & Hamid, 2017) leadership is someone who guides, guides, guides, builds, gives or awakens work motivation, drives the organization, establishes good organizational networks, allows efficient supervision or supervision and brings his followers to the desired target. targeted in accordance with the provisions of time and planning. (Hughes, Ginnet, & Curphy, 2018) suggests that there are four indicators that influence leadership , namely: (1) leadership directive; (2) leadership supportive; (3) leadership participle t iff; (4) leadership achievement oriented. This is supported by previous research which states that increased leadership will improve employee performance (Arief Teguh Nugroho 2018).

hypothesis 1 : Leadership has a positive effect on employee performance.

C. Intelligence Emotional

According to Robbins S. (2015) Emotional intelligence is a person's ability to detect and manage emotional cues and information. According to (Goleman, 2015) indicators intelligence emotional there are five indicators, namely: (1) emotional self-awareness; (2) Manage emotions; (3) Make use of emotions; and (4) Empathy; (5) build relationship. This is supported by previous research which states that intelligence increases emotional will improve employee performance (Wulandari, (2020).

hypothesis 2 : Intelligence emotional positive effect on employee performance.

D. Culture Organization

According to Fahmi (2017) "Organizational culture is the result of the process of fusing the cultural and behavioral styles of each individual previously brought into a new set of norms and philosophies, which have energy and group pride in dealing with certain things and goals".

According to Wirawan (2015) stated cultural indicators the organization consists of 4 (four) indicators, namely: (1) Implementation of norms; (2) Implementation of values; (3) Beliefs and philosophy Organizational beliefs; and (4) Implementation code ethics Code of ethics. This is supported by previous research which states that culture increases organization will improve employee performance (Nuning Lisdiana 2017).

hypothesis 3 : culture organization has a positive effect on employee performance.

Based on various study before, upgrade culture organization can be affected by the increase leadership (Nurul Huda, 2017) and improvement intelligence emotional (Wardani, et.al 2017).

hypothesis 4 : Leadership has a positive effect on culture organization .

hypothesis 5 : Intelligence emotional positive effect on culture organization .

In addition, several studies show that culture organization mediate leadership influence on employee performance (Nuning Lisdiana 2017), culture organization mediates the influence of intelligence emotional impact on employee performance (Fazira Isticarina (2021).

hypothesis 6 : culture organization mediates leadership on employee performance.

hypothesis 7 : culture organization mediates intelligence emotional impact on employee performance.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on background behind research and studies theory above, then framework conceptual study This can outlined as following:

Picture 1: Framework

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is explanatory research with approach designed quantitative for now influence leadership (X1) and intelligence emotional (X2) towards performance employee (Y2) culture organization (Y1) as mediating variable. Population in study This is d department Human Capital at PT Tribhakti Inspektama totaling 90 respondents. The sampling method used in the research This is with total sampling method, where all population made sample.

Data collection was carried out through instrument measuring questionnaire are below indicators of each variable. Obtained data Then processed and analyzed using SEM-PLS (Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least

Square). Every hypothesis will tested and analyzed through application SmartPLS.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Profiles of the Respondents

Respondents in study This is 90 employee's department Human Capital P T. TBI. Respondents consists of 62.2 % male and 37.8% female, 10% educated SLTA, 8.9% educated DIII, 7 0% educated Strata1 and 11.1% have a Master's degree. Based on distribution age, 51.1% aged 2 0 - 30 years and 34.4% aged 31-40 years, 10% aged 41-50, and 4.5 % aged > 50 years. Based on years of service, 14.4% worked for < 1 year, 56.7 % worked for 1-5 years, 18.9% worked for 6-10 years and 10 % worked for > 10 years year.

B. Measurements Model (Outer Model)

Table 1: Outer Model Results Summary

	Leadership	Intelligence Emotional	Culture Organization	Employee Performance
KP5	0.736			
KP6	0.795			
KP7	0.706			
KP8	0.771			
KP9	0.830			
KP10	0.843			
KP11	0.823			
KP12	0.771			
KP13	0.807			
KP16	0.725			
KE2		0.794		
KE7		0.792		
KE8		0.815		
KE9		0.870		
bo1			0.783	
bo3			0.734	
bo4			0.808	
BO5			0.797	
bo8			0.726	
KK2				0.724
KK3				0.736
KK4				0.749
KK5				0.793
KK6				0.804
KK8				0.753
KK9				0.787
KK10				0.782
KK11				0.777
KK13				0.793
KK14				0.753
KK15				0.742

Tabel 2: Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Value Results

	Average Variances Extracted (AVE)
Leadership	0.612
Intelligence Emotional	0.670
Culture Organization	0.593
Employee performance	0.587

C. Validity Test

➤ *Convergent validity*

Table 1 shows connection between construct with all question items with outer loading value > 0, 7 0. With thus,

all items have fulfilled condition validity convergent for study explanation (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 2 shows the value of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) ≥ 0.50, that is variation every variable in measurement items has fulfil validity good convergence.

➤ *Discriminant validity*

Table 3: HTMT

	Culture Organization	Intelligence Emotional	Leadership	Employee Performance
Culture Organization				
Intelligence Emotional	0.580			
Leadership	0.554	0.520		
Employee Performance	0.583	0.823	0.463	

Results in Table 3 above show that HTMT value has been fulfil criteria validity that is all value < 0.9 (Hair et al., 2019). That is, the variance shared by each variable taller for the measurement items If compared to by that divided by the item variable other. because that is, assessment validity discriminant with HTMT fulfilled.

➤ *Reliability Test*

After done testing validity construct, next reliability test was carried out measured construct _ with two criteria namely Composite Reliability (CR) and Cronbach's Alpha (CA) of measuring indicators _ CR construct is used for displays good reliability. Something construct stated reliable If composite reliability value or Cronbach's Alpha > 0.7, although 0.6 is still can accepted (Hair et. al, 2013).

Table 4: Cronbach Alpha and Composite reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Ket.
Leadership	0.929	0.940	Reliable
Intelligence Emotional	0.835	0.890	Reliable
Culture Organization	0.828	0879	Reliable
Employee Performance	0936	0.945	Reliable

Based on table 4, Cronbach's Alpha test results and composite reliability for all variable show value > 0.6. According to Hinton, et. al (2013) suggests four point covering reliability _ very good reliability (> 0.90),

➤ *Structural Model (Inner models)*

Coefficient of Determination Testing (R-Square/)

reliability high (0.70-0.90), reliability moderate (0.50-0.70) and reliability low (reliability low) <0.50. So, in research This its reliability is in very good category Because is above 0.9.

Table 5: R-Square

	R Square	R Square adjusted
Culture Organization	0.331	0.315
Employee performance	0.583	0.569

From the table above seen that R-Square value for variable culture organization of 0.331 which means that 33.1% contribution culture organization influenced by leadership and intelligence emotional, meanwhile the rest 66.9 % explained by factors other. Based on results data processing, obtained R-Square value for variable performance employee of 0.583 which means 58.3% contribution performance employee influenced by leadership, intelligence emotional and cultural organization,

meanwhile the rest of 41.7% explained. by factors other factors outside research.

➤ *Predictive Relevance (Q-Square)*

Predictive relevance (Q2) for structural models measures how much good mark observation generated. Predictive Relevance (Q2) for measuring structural models how much good mark observation generated by the model as well as the estimation the parameters.

Table 6: Predictive elevation (Q-Square)

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
	900,000	900,000	
Intelligence Emotional	360,000	360,000	
Culture Organization	450,000	372,623	0.172
Employee Performance	1080,000	736,577	0.318

Based on predictive relevance calculation (Q2) in Table 6 which shows mark variable Occupational Safety and Health (K3) (Y1) of 0.172 and value variable Employee Performance (Y2) of 0.318. Second value variable the bigger from 0 to can concluded that the model has mark relevant predictors.

➤ *Hypothesis testing*

Testing hypothesis use full model analysis of structural equation modeling (SEM) with smartPLS . In the full structural equation modeling model besides confirm theory, also explained There is or nope connection between latent variable. hypothesis said accepted if t- statistical value

bigger from the t- table and for reject or accept hypothesis

use mark probability, if the P-value < 0.05.

Picture 2: Bootstrapping results

➤ Hypothesis testing

Variable	Original Sampel (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistik	P Values	Ket.
			(O/STDEV)		
Kepemimpinan (X1) → Budaya Organisasi (Y1)	0.347	0.106	3.271	0.001	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Kecerdasan Emosional (X2) → Budaya Organisasi (Y1)	0.324	0.160	2.027	0.043	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Kepemimpinan (X1) → Kinerja Karyawan (Y2)	0.055	0.126	0.438	0.661	Tidak berpengaruh signifikan
Kecerdasan Emosional (X2) → Kinerja Karyawan (Y2)	0.625	0.107	5.846	0.000	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Budaya Organisasi (Y1) → Kinerja Karyawan (Y2)	0.185	0.128	1.443	0.150	Tidak berpengaruh signifikan

Variable	Original Sampel (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistik	P Values	Ket.
			(O/STDEV)		
Kepemimpinan (X1) → Budaya Organisasi (Y1) → Kinerja Karyawan (Y2)	0.060	0.066	0.910	0.363	Tidak berpengaruh signifikan
Kecerdasan Emosional (X2) → Budaya Organisasi (Y1) → Kinerja Karyawan (Y2)	0.064	0.050	1.287	0.199	Tidak berpengaruh signifikan

VI. DISCUSSION

H1 Influence leadership (X1) Against performance employee (Y2). I know mark coefficient path -0.055, t-statistic value 0.438 < 1.66) and P-Values = 0.661 > α = 0.05 . It means variable leadership (X1) no influential positive and significant to variable performance employee (Y2). With thereby hypothesis (H1) in study this is stated that " leadership (X1) is influential positive and significant on Employee Performance (Y2)" was rejected. this in line with results research conducted by Arief Teguh Nugroho (2018)

which state leadership No influential significant to performance.

H2 Influence intelligence emotional (X2) on Employee Performance (Y2). I know mark coefficient path 0.625, t-statistic value 5.846 < 1.66) and P- Values = 0.00 < α = 0.05. It means variable intelligence emotional influential positive and significant to variable Employee Performance. With thereby hypothesis (H2) in study this is stated that "intelligence emotional influential positive and significant on Employee Performance (Y2)" accepted. this _ in line

with results research conducted by Wulandari, (2020) which states intelligence emotional no influential to performance employee.

H3 Influence culture organization (Y1) on Employee Performance (Y2). I know mark coefficient path 0.185 t-statistic value $1.443 > 1.66$ and P-Values = $0.150 > \alpha = 0.05$. It means variable culture organization No influential positive and significant to variable Employee Performance. With thereby hypothesis (H3) in study this is stated that "culture organization influential positive and significant on Employee Performance" was rejected. this in line with results research conducted Nuning Lisdiana (2017) stated culture influential organization on Employee Performance.

H 4 Influence leadership (X1) Against culture organization (Y1). I know mark coefficient path 0.347, t-statistic value $3.271 < 1.98$ and P- Values = $0.001 < \alpha = 0.05$. It means variable leadership influential positive and significant to variable culture organization. With thereby hypothesis (H4) in study this is stated that "leadership influential positive and significant to culture organization" is accepted. This is in line with the results of research conducted by Nurul Huda, (2017) which states that leadership influences culture organization .

H 5 Influence intelligence emotional (X2) towards culture organization (Y2). I know mark coefficient path 0.324, t- statistic value $2.027 > 1.66$ and P- Values = $0.043 < \alpha = 0.05$. It means variable intelligence emotional influential positive and significant to variable culture organization. With thereby hypothesis (H5) in study this is stated that "intelligence emotional influential positive and significant to culture organization." accepted. This is in line with the research of Wardani, et.al (2017) which states intelligence Emotional influence on culture organization .

H 6 Influence leadership (X1) on Employee Performance (Y2) which is mediated by culture organization. (Y1). I know mark coefficient path 0.060, t-statistic value $0.910 < 1.66$ and P-Values = $0.363 > \alpha = 0.0$. It means variable leadership (X1) no influential to variable Employee Performance (Y2) which is mediated by culture organization (Y1). With thereby hypothesis (H6) in study this is stated that " leadership (X1) is influential positive and significant to variable Employee Performance (Y2) which is mediated by culture organization (Y1)" was rejected. This is in line with Nuning Lisdiana's research (2017) which states culture organization No can mediate leadership on employee performance.

H 7 Influence intelligence emotional (X2) on Employee Performance (Y2) which is mediated by culture organization (Y1). I know mark coefficient path 0.064, t-statistic value $1.287 < 1.66$ and P-Values = $0.199 > \alpha = 0.05$. It means variable intelligence emotional (X2) no influential to variable Employee Performance (Y2) which is mediated by culture organization (Y1). With thereby hypothesis (H7) in study this is stated that "intelligence emotional (X2) effect positive and significant to variable Employee Performance (Y2) which is mediated by culture organization (Y1)" was rejected. this No in line with study Fazira Isticarina (2021)

stated culture organization can mediate culture organization to performance employee.

VII. CONCLUSION

Study This conclude as following: leadership No influential to performance employees, intelligence emotional influential positive and significant to performance employees, culture organization No influential to performance employee, leadership influential positive and significant to culture organization, intelligence emotional influential positive and significant to culture organization, culture the organization does not mediate leadership influence to performance employees, culture organization does not mediate the influence of intelligence emotional to performance employee.

Study This own a number of limitations . Study This only analyze leadership and intelligence emotional and cultural organization as influencing variables performance employee. In relation with matter such, research more carry on can done at the company other or scope more population broad. Study further is also necessary consider for use other influencing variables performance, like compensation, engagement work, motivation work, satisfaction work, support perceived organization, psychological capital, justice procedural and variable other.

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